

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Plant Diversity Boosts Soil Self-Regulation and Fungivores in German Wheat Cultivation

The goal of this study is to find out whether increasing plant diversity in conventional wheat farming can help reduce fungal diseases, especially Fusarium, by encouraging beneficial soil organisms that feed on fungi. The study also looks at how plant diversity can improve the soil's natural ability to regulate itself.

In the first year of the experiment, 2021, three types of treatments were used. The first treatment (T1) served as the control and involved conventional wheat farming with regular plant protection methods and narrow seed rows spaced 12.5 cm apart. The second treatment (T2) used a more extensive approach, with wider seed rows without plant protection. The third treatment (T3) added even more diversity by combining wide seed rows, no plant protection, and sowing a mix of clover species underneath the wheat.

The second and third treatments were designed to increase plant diversity in the field, with the third treatment also boosting the number of different sown species. Aside from these differences, all other farming practices, such as fertilization and soil preparation, were kept the same across all treatments.

In the following two growing seasons, 2022 and 2023, all the plots were managed according to local farming practices. This setup allowed researchers to observe any lasting effects from the treatments applied in 2021 and how they influenced the soil and crops over time.

Tables

The following table presents the average values of crop revenue, direct costs, and calculated gross margins for each crop cycle and the overall crop rotation. The revenue variability was impacted by the yields as those varied considerably across the cases. The producer price for wheat in 2021 was around 190 €/t which was considerably lower in comparison with following years in which the producer prices for wheat increased quickly.

The direct costs were higher for fields with experimental treatment 3 (diversified extensive farming). The gross margin for wheat in 2021 ranged between 763 €/ha under the conventional cropping to 600 €/ha under the extensive farming treatment that had very low yields.

	Costs (€/ha)	Revenues (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Control (Conventional Wheat)	1,110	1,873	763
T2: T1 + wider seed rows + no plant protection	1,063	1,663	600
T3: T2 + undersown crops	1,176	1,907	731

1. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 3-year rotation (winter wheat-silage maize - winter wheat).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, self-regulation, wheat cultivation, fungivores

AUTHORSHIP

Birte Tschentke, Flächenagentur Rheinland, Germany
David-Alexander Bind, Flächenagentur Rheinland, Germany
Martin Banse, Thünen Institute, Germany
Christine van Capelle, Thünen Institute, Germany

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

This factsheet is produced as part of the SoildiverAgro project. Although the author has worked on the best information available, neither the author nor the EU shall in any event be liable for any loss, damage or injury incurred directly or indirectly in relation to the project.